

CORRELATING MATRIX AND COMPOSITE FRACTURE RESPONSE AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

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ABSTRACT

Most fiber-reinforced plastics exhibit reduced fracture strength at cryogenic temperatures. However, the interlaminar fracture toughness of the commercial glass-polyester composite Extren at 77K (liquid nitrogen temperature) exceeds that at 298K (room temperature). The fracture toughness/response of Extren and a glass-epoxy composite (G10-CR) are correlated here with that of their respective matrix materials in an effort to better understand these events.

1. INTRODUCTION

The interlaminar fracture behavior of commercial Extren (glass-polyester) and G10-CR (glass-epoxy) has been investigated at room temperature (298K), dry ice temperature (194.4K) and liquid nitrogen temperature (77K) [1,2]. Although the fracture toughness of most fiber-reinforced plastics decreases with decreasing temperature, Extren behaves differently [1-5]. Unlike G10-CR, Extren's delamination fracture energy is greater at cryogenic temperature than at room temperature. The fracture toughness of a composite depends on its fiber/matrix interface bond and micro structure, and mechanical properties of its matrix. This paper discusses the measured fracture toughness of the Extren and G10-CR composites relative to that of their matrix materials.

2. FRACTURE OF GLASS-POLYESTER AND GLASS-EPOXY COMPOSITES [1,2]

The interlaminar fracture behavior of Extren and G10-CR composites has been studied previously at 298K, 194.4K and 77K, and the results are summarized in Table 1.

Figures 1 and 2 are representative load vs. deflection (or time) data from width tapered double cantilever beam (WTDCB) specimens of these composites tested at the three temperatures. At 298K and 194.4K, crack growth in Extren is continuous and stable at a speed determined largely by that of the testing machine. At 77K, Extren exhibits rapid, unstable and intermittent crack growth (stick-slip) whose speed is independent of the testing speed. Load-deflection curves of 77K Extren specimens typically have a "saw-tooth" appearance. G10-CR also exhibits smooth,

continuous load-deflection curves associated with stable crack-growth at 298K and 194.4K, and a "saw-tooth" appearance at 77K, Figure 2.

Whereas the interlaminar fracture energy of G10-CR decreases monotonically with decreasing temperature, Extren behaves otherwise, Table 1. Extren's fracture energy is 1032 J/m² at 298K, 763 J/m² at 194.4K and 1524 J/m² at 77K.

Extren exhibits clean, relatively undisturbed fracture surfaces at 298K. This composite shows hackle-like patterns when tested at 77K, although not at 298K or 194.4K. Hackle patterns and micro-crack branching have been observed in G10-CR failed at all three temperatures considered here. Crack growth in G10-CR tends to remain in-plane at 194.4K and 77K, whereas that at 298K cuts across adjacent plies.

3. EXPERIMENTAL

3.1 Materials and Specimen Preparation

Non-reinforced matrix (polyester and epoxy) compact-tension (C-T) fracture specimens were prepared and tested to determine fracture properties. The polyester is the Extren matrix material, and the unfilled epoxy is virtually the same as the epoxy resin used in G10-CR.

Sheets of the resins were fabricated using conventional casting techniques, from which the C-T fracture specimens were machined [6]. The same catalysts as those used in commercial Extren and G10-CR were added to the resin gels. The room-temperature cure time was 2 hours for the polyester resin and 6 hours for the epoxy resin.

3.2 Fracture Toughness Determination

The fracture toughness of each of these two resins was determined using standard C-T testing techniques, specimen geometry and dimensions [7,8]. Values of the fracture toughness K_{IC} were determined at each temperature (298K, 194.4K and 77K) from measured values of the critical load P_c using the expression [7]:

$$K_{IC} = YP_c/BW^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{where } Y = 29.6(a/W)^{1/2} - 185.5(a/W)^{3/2} + 655.7(a/W)^{5/2} - 1017(a/W)^{7/2} + 638.9(a/W)^{9/2}$$

and a , $B = 1.9$ cm and W are the conventional dimensions of the standard C-T fracture specimen, Fig. 3. The fracture energy (critical crack-extension force) G_c is related to the fracture toughness (critical stress intensity factor) K_{IC} , i.e., $K_{IC}^2 = G_c E$ for plane stress and $K_{IC}^2 = G_c E/(1-\nu^2)$ for plane strain. The measured constitutive properties of these matrix materials were obtained from Refs. 4 and 9.

Machined and pre-cracked C-T resin specimens were tested using a MTS 810 tensile machine, under displacement control at a rate of 0.05cm/min (0.02in/min). When testing at liquid nitrogen temperature (77K), a specimen was first set into the nitrogen fumes and then slowly lowered into the actual liquid. This was done to prevent immediate cracking of the unfilled polymer resin which would occur if a resin specimen were placed directly into the liquid nitrogen. Testing at dry ice temperature (194.4K) was accomplished by first maintaining the specimen in dry ice for about thirty minutes and then removing the specimen for testing.

4. RESULTS

Three C-T specimens of each resin were tested at each of the three temperatures. Load vs. displacement information was recorded continuously during each test, Figures 4 and 5. These Figures give ultimate (critical) loads P_c of 1156N (260 lb) at 298K, 578N (130 lb) at 194.4K and 298N (67 lb) at 77K for the polyester, and 636N (143 lb) at 298K, 431N (97 lb) at 194.4K and 209N (47 lb) at 77K for the epoxy. The fracture toughness values of Table 2 were obtained from these data and Equation (1).

5. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The fracture toughness of the polyester exceeds that of the epoxy at each of the temperatures considered, although the epoxy-based G10-CR composite is tougher than Extren at each of these temperatures, Tables 1 and 2. Unlike the Extren, the toughness K_{Ic} of both matrix materials decreases monotonically with decreasing temperature.

It seems generally reasonable that an decrease in toughness of the matrix resin would decrease the toughness of the corresponding composite [10-12]. Polymers tend to be more brittle at cryogenic temperature than at room temperature [3,4]. One might therefore expect the fracture energy of a reinforced polymeric composite to decrease as the temperature decreases [3-5].

Notwithstanding the comments immediately above, the fracture response/toughness of reinforced plastics are much more complicated than that of their unfilled matrix. The fracture energy of Extren is higher at 298K than at 194.4K, compatible with the trend in toughness of its polyester matrix, Tables 1 and 2. However, Extren's fracture energy is considerably higher at 77K than at either 298K or 194.4K. On the other hand, the fracture toughness of both G10-CR and its epoxy matrix decreases monotonically with decreasing temperature. There is also substantial difference in microstructure between the Extren and G10-CR composites.

Since hackle pattern formation in Extren at 77K dissipates energy, a greater energy release rate is needed to initiate crack growth in this composite at this temperature than at 194.4K or 198K. This hackle pattern formation therefore helps to increase the interlaminar fracture toughness of Extren at 77K. However, the relatively low fracture toughness of the polyester matrix at 77K causes a macro-crack, once initiated in Extren, to propagate through the matrix at a rate exceeding the cross-head speed of the loading machine. This rapid crack growth continues until sufficient energy has been dissipated to arrest the crack. This process might then repeat itself several times until the specimen fails. Such starts and stops typically produce a load-deflection curve for Extren at 77K which is "saw-tooth" in appearance, Figure 1.

Extren shows relatively stable crack growth at both 298K and 194.4K. Hackle patterns have not been observed in the polyester matrix of this composite when failed at either of these two temperatures [1,2], and Extren exhibits virtually identical fracture mechanics at both of these temperatures. The delamination fracture toughness of Extren is influenced by the fracture toughness of its polyester matrix. Fracture toughness of Extren is lower at 194.4K than at 298K, which is compatible with the temperature variation of the fracture toughness of the polyester resin.

Fractured surfaces of G10-CR tested at either of the three temperatures show hackle patterns, and its fracture process shows some similarities at all three temperatures. The fracture toughness of the glass-epoxy decreases as the temperature decrease. This is compatible with the monotonic decrease in toughness with temperature of the epoxy, and the strong dependence of composite toughness on that of its matrix material.

6. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

The interlaminar fracture toughness of a glass-reinforced plastic depends typically on its fracture mechanisms and on the toughness of its matrix material. The temperature change in fracture toughness of glass-epoxy G10-CR follows that of its epoxy matrix. However, the behavior of glass-polyester Extren is more complicated. Extren exhibits nearly identical fracture mechanisms at 298K and 194.4K. However, it has a lower interlaminar fracture toughness at 194.4K than at 298K. This trend agrees with the toughness trend of its polyester matrix. Extren shows a different fracture mechanism at 77K. Its fracture toughness at 77K is higher than that at either 194.4K or 298K, even though the toughness of its polyester matrix is lowest at 77K.

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Table 1. Interlaminar Fracture Energy of Extren and G10-CR

Temperature	Fracture Energy G _{IC} (J/m ²)	
	Extren	G10-CR
298K	1032	3450
194.4K	763	2937
77K	1524	2683

Table 2. Fracture Toughness of Unfilled Resins Determined from the C-T Specimens

Material	Temp	Critical Load (N)	Fracture Toughness K _{IC} (MPa√m)
Polyester	298K	1156	2.98
Polyester	194.4K	578	1.50
Polyester	77K	298	0.77
Epoxy	298K	636	1.65
Epoxy	194.4K	431	1.12
Epoxy	77K	209	0.53

Figure 1. Load-time (deflection) Response of Extren WTDC Beams.

Figure 2. Load-time (deflection) Response of G10-CR WTDC Beams

Figure 3. Compact-Tension Resin Specimen

Figure 4. Load-Time (deflection) Response of Unfilled Polyester C-T Specimens

Figure 5. Load-Time (deflection) Response of Unfilled Epoxy C-T Specimens.